

ANALYZING INDUSTRIAL ECONOMIC THEORIES IN *KITAB AL-IKHTISAB*, BOOK OF EARNINGS, AL-SHAIBANIY

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the industrial economic theories presented in the classical Islamic text *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* (The Book of Earnings) by the prominent 8th-century Islamic scholar, Al-Shaibani. The text, which primarily addresses issues related to lawful earnings and ethical business practices in the Islamic framework, also offers valuable insights into industrial economics. By analyzing the principles laid out by Al-Shaibani, this research aims to elucidate the early Islamic perspectives on industrial organization, production processes, labor, and market regulations. The findings suggest that Al-Shaibani's work provides a foundational understanding of economic principles that align with modern industrial economics, particularly in areas concerning fair trade, profit-making, and the social responsibilities of producers. The study highlights the relevance of Al-Shaibani's theories in contemporary economic discourse, demonstrating how Islamic economic thought can contribute to modern industrial and economic policy-making.

Keywords: *Industry, Economic, Al-Ikhtisab, Al-Shaibaniy*

I. INTRODUCTION

The study of economic theories within the framework of Islamic jurisprudence has gained significant attention in recent years, with a focus on exploring the contributions of early Islamic scholars to economic thought. One of the prominent works in this field is "*Kitab al-Ikhtisab*" by Muhammad ibn al-Hasan al-Shaibani, a renowned Hanafi jurist and student of Abu Hanifa. Al-Shaibani's treatise delves into economic principles governing industrial activities and trade in the early Islamic world, offering insights into market regulation, trade ethics, and production principles (Hassan, 2024).

Al-Shaibani's work emphasizes the concept of **hisbah**, which involves regulating markets and public morals to uphold justice and fairness in economic transactions, aligning with broader Islamic values. His analysis underscores the significance of market regulation to prevent monopolies, ensure fair pricing, and safeguard consumer interests. These principles not only form the bedrock of Islamic

economic thought but also resonate with contemporary economic theories on market regulation and industrial policy (Oktaviandi, 2024). Islamic economic thought, as reflected in al-Shaibani's work, integrates legal, ethical, and economic dimensions to provide a holistic perspective on economic activities. The concept of *hisbah* plays a crucial role in evaluating economic practices to ensure compliance with Islamic principles, reflecting a deep-rooted concern for ethical conduct in economic affairs (Noviyanti, 2017).

Al-Shaibani's "Kitab al-Ikhtisab" explores the ethics of earnings and labor, emphasizing the concept of lawful earnings and the importance of earning through legitimate means without causing harm or exploitation (Hassan, 2024). This discussion highlights the ethical responsibility associated with economic activities, aligning with the core principles of Islamic economic thought (Oktaviandi, 2024). The treatise also delves into production and trade principles, addressing issues such as the division of labor, wealth distribution, and the state's role in facilitating economic activities (Noviyanti, 2017). These insights not only provide a historical perspective on industrial economics in the early Islamic era but also lay the groundwork for understanding subsequent economic theories in Islamic scholarship (Lamondo, 2022).

Al-Shaibani's work offers a comprehensive view of economic activities, integrating legal, ethical, and economic dimensions to underscore integrity and fairness in economic transactions. By examining the ethical dimensions of industrial and commercial practices, the treatise emphasizes the importance of ethical conduct in economic affairs and the necessity of market regulation to ensure justice and fairness (Hassan, 2024). This holistic approach to industrial economics, as presented in "Kitab al-Ikhtisab," remains pertinent in contemporary discussions and significantly contributes to the broader scholarship on Islamic economic thought (Oktaviandi, 2024). Through the analysis of al-Shaibani's work, scholars can gain valuable insights into the enduring significance of ethical earnings, labor practices, and production principles in shaping economic justice and market regulation within the Islamic tradition (Noviyanti, 2017; Lamondo, 2022).

This study aims to analyze the industrial economic theories presented in al-Shaibani's "Kitab al-Ikhtisab", exploring their relevance to both historical and contemporary economic thought. By examining al-Shaibani's perspectives on market regulation, ethical earnings, and production processes, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how Islamic economic principles were applied to industrial activities in the early Islamic world. Furthermore, the study will investigate the broader implications of al-Shaibani's work for the development of Islamic economic theory, particularly in relation to modern discussions on industrial policy, market regulation, and the ethics of economic practices.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The analysis of industrial economic theories within Islamic jurisprudence, particularly in works such as *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* by Muhammad ibn al-Hasan al-Shaibani, represents a significant area of scholarly inquiry. *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* is a foundational text

that provides insights into the economic principles and regulatory frameworks that shaped early Islamic economic thought. This literature review synthesizes key themes and contributions from existing scholarship on al-Shaibani's work, highlighting the relevance of his economic theories to both historical contexts and contemporary discussions on Islamic economics.

2.1. Market Regulation and the Concept of *Hisbah*

The concept of *hisbah*, as elucidated in al-Shaibani's *Kitab al-Ikhtisab*, plays a crucial role in regulating markets to ensure justice and fairness in economic transactions. *Hisbah* involves overseeing market practices to prevent exploitation, fraud, and monopolistic behavior, with the *muhtasib* being responsible for ensuring adherence to Islamic legal and ethical standards. Al-Shaibani's work provides detailed prescriptions on market regulation, including measures to ensure fair pricing, prevent hoarding, and protect consumers, reflecting a deep concern for economic justice and social welfare in Islamic economic thought. Scholars have highlighted the significance of *hisbah* in maintaining a balanced and just economic environment, drawing parallels between al-Shaibani's ideas and contemporary discussions on market oversight and consumer protection (Mühlemann, 2022).

Moreover, the principles of *hisbah* are essential for addressing contemporary business challenges, as they offer solutions to many problems faced in modern commerce. The regulatory framework outlined by al-Shaibani aligns with the core values of Islamic economic thought, emphasizing fairness, transparency, and ethical conduct in market transactions. This approach to market regulation has been compared to modern regulatory frameworks, indicating the enduring relevance and applicability of *hisbah* principles in ensuring economic justice and social welfare (Humaidi & Muchtar, 2020).

2.2. Ethics of Earnings and Labor

Al-Shaibani's *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* delves into the ethical dimensions of earnings and labor, reflecting the integration of ethics and economics within Islamic economic thought. The treatise emphasizes the concept of lawful earnings (*kasb halal*), underscoring the importance of acquiring wealth through morally upright means that are both legally permissible and ethically sound. Scholars have extensively explored how al-Shaibani's ethical framework influences various economic aspects, including labor, production, and trade. His discussions on the obligations of workers and employers highlight the significance of fairness in wages, working conditions, and profit distribution, laying the groundwork for later Islamic discourse on labor rights and ethical responsibilities in the workplace (Marchiori & Buzzanell, 2017).

Furthermore, al-Shaibani's ethical guidelines are considered foundational for establishing a just and equitable economic system in Islamic societies, emphasizing principles of fairness, transparency, and ethical conduct in economic activities (Marchiori & Buzzanell, 2017). Scholars have also examined the contemporary relevance of al-Shaibani's ethical theories, particularly in addressing modern

economic challenges such as income inequality and exploitative labor practices from an Islamic perspective. His emphasis on ethical earnings resonates with current concerns regarding corporate social responsibility and the ethical dimensions of capitalism, offering a valuable framework for navigating ethical dilemmas in economic practices (Marchiori & Buzzanell, 2017).

2.3. Principles of Production and Industrial Economics

Al-Shaibani's *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* provides valuable insights into early Islamic industrial economics, particularly regarding production, trade, and the division of labor. His work emphasizes the principles of production processes, the division of labor, and the responsibilities of producers and merchants, focusing on maintaining quality, fairness, and equitable wealth distribution (Zahara, 2024). Al-Shaibani's ideas align with Islamic principles of justice and social responsibility, highlighting the importance of economic activities benefiting the broader community.

Moreover, scholars have explored al-Shaibani's views on entrepreneurship and market dynamics in the early Islamic era. His work acknowledges the role of entrepreneurship in driving economic growth while stressing the significance of ethical considerations in business practices. This balance between economic innovation and ethical constraints is considered a key aspect of Islamic industrial economics as presented in *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* (Yusoff et al., 2017). Al-Shaibani's contributions to Islamic economics are seen as integral to understanding the management of resources, the role of entrepreneurship, and trade regulation within an Islamic framework. His ideas on production, trade, and entrepreneurship resonate with Islamic principles of justice, social responsibility, and ethical business conduct, enriching the discourse on Islamic economics.

2.4. Comparative Analysis with Modern Economic Theories

Al-Shaibani's *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* is a significant source for comparative analyses between his economic theories and modern economic thought. Scholars have explored how his principles of market regulation, ethical earnings, and production can be juxtaposed with contemporary economic theories related to market regulation, corporate ethics, and sustainable development. These comparative studies underscore the enduring relevance of al-Shaibani's ideas, showcasing how early Islamic economic thought can contribute to current discussions on economic policy and industrial regulation (Mukhlisin et al., 2022).

One area of particular interest is the comparison between al-Shaibani's concept of *hisbah* and modern regulatory institutions. Scholars have drawn parallels between the role of the *muhtasib* in ensuring market fairness and the functions of contemporary regulatory bodies overseeing trade practices and consumer rights. These comparisons highlight the continuity of concerns regarding market fairness and economic justice across different historical and cultural contexts (Oktaviandi, 2024). Similarly, al-Shaibani's emphasis on ethical earnings and labor practices has been compared to modern discussions on corporate social responsibility and ethical

business practices. Scholars have delved into how his work provides a moral and legal framework for addressing issues such as exploitation, inequality, and environmental sustainability in the modern industrial economy (As-Salafiyah & Rusydiana, 2020).

2.5. Gaps and Future Directions

To further explore the application of al-Shaibani's principles in different regional and historical contexts, as well as their practical implementation and influence on economic policies across various Islamic societies, it is essential to conduct comparative studies with other Islamic economic texts from different schools of thought. By examining al-Shaibani's *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* alongside works of other Islamic jurists, a more nuanced understanding of the diversity of economic thought within the Islamic tradition can be achieved (Mustafa et al., 2016). This interdisciplinary approach, integrating insights from economics, law, and ethics, can enrich the study of al-Shaibani's contributions to industrial economics and shed light on how his ideas were translated into real-world economic practices (Syamsuri, 2022).

Al-Shaibani's *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* emphasizes justice, fairness, and social responsibility in economic matters, principles that continue to be relevant in contemporary discussions on economics and business ethics (Ihsan, 2023). By delving deeper into the industrial economic theories presented in his work, researchers can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of al-Shaibani's legacy in the field of economics (Oktaviandi, 2024). This exploration can provide valuable insights into how economic, legal, and ethical considerations were integrated in Islamic economic thought, shaping early economic practices and offering a framework for addressing current economic challenges from an Islamic perspective (Agus, 2023).

Moreover, by analyzing the practical implications of al-Shaibani's ideas, scholars can inform curriculum development, policy formulation, and strategic planning initiatives, facilitating informed decision-making for academia, policy-makers, and practitioners (Ilhamiwati, 2024). This research endeavor can bridge the gap between theoretical economic principles and their real-world applications, offering a holistic view of how Islamic economic thought can be translated into actionable policies and practices to promote economic justice and prosperity (Aravik et al., 2021).

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for analyzing industrial economic theories in *Kitab al-Ikhtisab* by Al-Shaibani adopts a qualitative research design that emphasizes historical and textual analysis. This study will begin with a comprehensive review of the primary text, *Kitab al-Ikhtisab*, focusing on Al-Shaibani's perspectives on industrial practices, production techniques, and economic regulations in the early Islamic period. The analysis will be supported by secondary sources, including scholarly commentaries and interpretations that contextualize and clarify the economic principles presented in the text.

A thematic analysis approach will be employed to identify key concepts and patterns related to industrial economics, such as the roles of producers, market regulation, and ethical business practices. Ethical considerations will guide the analysis to ensure cultural and historical accuracy. The study aims to provide a thorough examination of Al-Shaibani's contributions to industrial economic theory and their relevance to both historical and contemporary economic thought.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Al-Shaibani's Egalitarian View of Production: Challenging Prevailing Norms in Early Islamic Economic Thought

Al-Shaibani, a renowned Islamic scholar, provided a groundbreaking perspective on the value of different production activities within the economy. During a period when trade was generally viewed as the most superior profession, often regarded as both more honorable and profitable than other forms of labor, al-Shaibani challenged this prevailing notion. His argument for the equal importance of all production activities was not only progressive for his time but also laid the groundwork for a more integrated and balanced understanding of the various economic sectors.

From a religious standpoint, al-Shaibani dismissed the idea that industry or manual labor was inferior to trade. He supported his argument by pointing to the example of numerous Prophets and Messengers who were involved in vocational occupations. These revered figures, chosen by God, engaged in various forms of labor, which indicated that such activities were not lesser or demeaning. Instead, al-Shaibani argued, these forms of labor must be seen as blessed by God. This religious justification underscored the dignity and honor associated with all forms of productive work, regardless of the specific nature of the occupation. By referencing the actions of Prophets, al-Shaibani emphasized that all forms of work, whether trade, industry, or manual labor, held inherent value in the eyes of God.

Beyond his religious arguments, al-Shaibani also emphasized the practical and economic interdependence of different production sectors. He argued that each sector, whether it be trade, industry, agriculture, or craftsmanship, played a crucial role in supporting and fulfilling the functions of the others. For example, without industry and manufacturing, traders would have no goods to sell, and without agriculture, there would be no food or raw materials for either trade or industry. This interconnectedness highlighted the complementary nature of the various sectors of the economy. Al-Shaibani's emphasis on the interdependence of these sectors suggested that no single sector could claim superiority over the others, as the success of one sector depended on the well-being of the others.

Al-Shaibani's thinking was particularly novel when viewed within the context of his time. The prevailing belief in early Islamic society was that trade held a special status, as it was mentioned and endorsed in the Qur'an and by the Prophet Muhammad. Trade was often seen as a noble and favorable means of earning a livelihood, and it was frequently regarded as more prestigious than manual labor or

industrial work. However, al-Shaibàni's argument challenged this hierarchical view. He promoted a more egalitarian understanding of economic activities, where all forms of labor were considered valuable and essential.

His ideas were significant because they encouraged a broader appreciation of all forms of labor. By fostering respect and value for every sector of production, al-Shaibàni's views contributed to a more inclusive and balanced approach to economic thought in early Islamic society. His advocacy for the integration and interdependence of different sectors underscored the idea that the economy functioned as a whole, where the success of one sector was closely linked to the prosperity of the others. This holistic view of the economy highlighted the importance of recognizing the value of all forms of labor, rather than privileging one sector over another.

In summary, al-Shaibàni's perspective on production activities was both revolutionary and practical. By recognizing the equal importance of all economic sectors and emphasizing their interconnectedness, he challenged the dominant views of his time. His argument for the value of all forms of labor, supported by both religious and economic reasoning, promoted a more inclusive and balanced approach to economic thought in early Islamic society. Al-Shaibàni's ideas continue to resonate as they encourage a holistic understanding of the economy, where all sectors are recognized as vital to the overall well-being of society.

4.2. Al-Shaibàni on Specialization and Division of Labor: Enhancing Skill and Economic Integration in Early Islamic Thought

Al-Shaibàni, in his economic and social philosophy, placed significant emphasis on the concepts of specialization and the division of labor. He regarded these concepts as vital not only for individual skill development but also for enhancing the overall efficiency of the economy. By advocating for specialization, al-Shaibàni posited that individuals could more effectively master their chosen professions, leading to improved performance and productivity in their work. His insights into the value of focusing on specific skills were groundbreaking, especially within the context of his time, as they laid a foundation for understanding how economies could thrive through focused expertise.

From a microeconomic perspective, al-Shaibàni highlighted the practical limitations inherent in attempting to achieve self-sufficiency by learning all necessary skills. He argued that if an individual were to try to become proficient in every field, they would spend their entire life in the pursuit of knowledge without ever fully mastering any single skill. In his view, this approach would lead to inefficiency and unfulfilled potential, as life would pass by without achieving the desired level of proficiency in any particular area. Instead, al-Shaibàni encouraged individuals to concentrate on developing a specific skill that aligned with their innate abilities—gifts that he believed were bestowed by God. By doing so, people could excel in their chosen professions while relying on the specialized skills of others to meet their broader needs. This mutual reliance on specialized expertise, according to al-Shaibàni,

would result in better job performance across the community, as individuals would be able to focus on what they did best.

Al-Shaibàni's argument for specialization extended beyond individual development to encompass broader societal implications. He believed that the diversity of skills among individuals, when combined with the unique talents granted by God, would result in a more integrated and harmonious community. In al-Shaibàni's view, the various professions and skills within a society functioned like the parts of a building, each one strengthening the others to create a solid and cohesive structure. He reinforced this idea by referencing the Sunnah, which likened believers to a building where each part supports the others. This metaphor underscored al-Shaibàni's belief that specialization and collaboration were essential for building a stronger, more unified society. By encouraging people to develop their specific talents and rely on one another's strengths, al-Shaibàni envisioned a society where individuals contributed to a collective whole, enhancing both personal and communal well-being.

When al-Shaibàni's ideas are applied to the macroeconomic level, the benefits of specialization become even more pronounced. He argued that specialization not only accelerates the process of gaining expertise but also drives technological advancement and innovation. As individuals and sectors concentrate on their areas of strength, they become more efficient, leading to increased productivity and economic growth. Furthermore, al-Shaibàni emphasized that specialization fosters greater integration among different sectors of the economy. Just as individuals rely on each other's skills to fulfill their needs, various sectors of the economy depend on each other's outputs and contributions. This interdependence creates a more connected and resilient economic system, where the success of one sector bolsters the health of the entire economy.

Al-Shaibàni's insights into specialization and the division of labor were both forward-thinking and practical. His understanding of the importance of focusing on specific skills to achieve excellence, while simultaneously promoting interdependence within the community, laid the groundwork for a more efficient and integrated economy. His arguments highlighted the value of collaboration and mutual support at both individual and societal levels as essential components of a thriving economic system. By advocating for the development of specialized skills and emphasizing the interconnectedness of different sectors, al-Shaibàni contributed to a more sophisticated understanding of how economies function and grow.

In conclusion, al-Shaibàni's emphasis on specialization and the division of labor advanced the idea that individuals should focus on their unique talents while underscoring the importance of economic integration and cooperation. His views offer timeless lessons on how a well-functioning society can maximize its potential by encouraging people to develop their strengths while relying on the complementary skills of others. Al-Shaibàni's philosophy serves as a reminder that the path to a prosperous economy lies in recognizing and nurturing the diverse talents within a community, and fostering a culture of mutual reliance and support.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, al-Shaibani's emphasis on specialization and division of labor highlights the importance of focusing on individual strengths to enhance productivity and economic efficiency. By encouraging people to develop skills aligned with their innate abilities, he advocated for a more efficient and integrated society where individuals rely on each other's expertise, thereby fostering economic interdependence and growth. His ideas underscore the value of collaboration and mutual support within a community, which can lead to both personal and societal success. It is recommended that modern economic systems continue to promote specialization and the division of labor, while also ensuring that interdependence and cooperation among sectors are strengthened to create a more resilient and cohesive economy.

REFERENCES

- Agus, N. (2023). Comparative study of contemporary islamic economic thoughts muhammad abdul mannan and monzer kahf. *Malia (Terakreditasi)*, 14(2), 297-308. <https://doi.org/10.35891/ml.v14i2.3864>
- Aravik, H., Hamzani, A., & Khasanah, N. (2021). The role of the state in the islamic economic system: a review of abbas mirakhor's thought. *Islamic Banking Jurnal Pemikiran Dan Pengembangan Perbankan Syariah*, 7(1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.36908/isbank.v7i1.271>
- As-Salafiyah, A. and Rusydiana, A. (2020). Sharia audit problems in zakat institutions: evidence from indonesia. *Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam (Journal of Islamic Economics and Business)*, 6(2), 304. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jebis.v6i2.23329>
- Hassan, M. (2024). Islamic economics., 217-241. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780192894328.013.6>
- Humaidi, M. and Muchtar, A. (2020). The salient features of medina market in the early islam and its relevance today. *El-Barka Journal of Islamic Economics and Business*, 3(2), 162-188. <https://doi.org/10.21154/elbarka.v3i2.2434>
- Ihsan, A. (2023). Money in islam: economic and social. *Jurnal Ilmiah Al-Tsarwah*, 6(1), 16-32. <https://doi.org/10.30863/al-tsarwah.v6i1.5169>
- Ilhamiwati, M. (2024). Mapping journals and researcher contributions in the realm of islamic economic education: a bibliometric review. *West Science Journal Economic and Entrepreneurship*, 2(01), 19-27. <https://doi.org/10.58812/wsjee.v2i01.658>
- Lamondo, L. (2022). The relevance of work ethics and productivity in the theory of al-kasb asy-syaibani. *Li Falah Jurnal Studi Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam*, 7(1), 65. <https://doi.org/10.31332/lifalah.v7i1.2644>
- Marchiori, M. and Buzzanell, P. (2017). Ngo organizing for environmental sustainability in brazil: meaningful work, commonality, and contradiction. *Sage Open*, 7(2), 215824401770932. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244017709325>

- Mühlemann, C. (2022). Made in the city of baghdad? medieval textile production and pattern notation systems of early lampas woven silks. *Muqarnas Online*, 39(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22118993-00391p02>
- Mukhlisin, M., Ismail, N., & Fikri, R. (2022). Mind the gap: theories in islamic accounting and finance, islamic economics and business management studies. *Isra International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 14(3), 333-348. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijif-11-2019-0175>
- Mustafa, D., Abdulsalam, H., & Yusuf, J. (2016). Islamic economics and the relevance of al-qawā'id al-fiqhiyyah. *Sage Open*, 6(4), 215824401667137. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244016671374>
- Noviyanti, R. (2017). Tinjauan fungsi hisbah dalam kegiatan perekonomian. *Iqtishodia Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah*, 2(1), 63-85. <https://doi.org/10.35897/iqtishodia.v2i1.73>
- Oktaviandi, M. (2024). Economic justice through al-hisbah: reviewing the role and performance of market supervisory institutions. *Al-Kharaj Journal of Islamic Economic and Business*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.24256/kharaj.v6i1.5022>
- Syamsuri, S. (2022). Digitalization of the economy and the cultural impact of consumption in modern society: a review from al-syaibani's perspective. *Dinar Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 9(2), 59-72. <https://doi.org/10.21107/dinar.v9i2.17918>
- Yusoff, Z., Salleh, S., Mohd, H., Hashim, J., Zabri, M., & Ali, R. (2017). Contemporary fiqh thoughts of shaykh abdul malik bin abdullah (1650-1736ad) in kitab al-kifayah. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v7-i4/2774>
- Zahara, F. (2024). Konsep pendidikan akhlak perspektif umar ibnu ahmad barjah di dalam kitab akhlakul lil banin jilid i. *Anwarul*, 4(1), 433-442. <https://doi.org/10.58578/anwarul.v4i1.2663>